

Does copper contamination change thermotaxis of the soil arthropod *Folsomia candida* (Collembola)?

Jian Ge^{a,*}, Stine Slotsbo^a, Jesper Givskov Sørensen^b, Martin Holmstrup^a

^a Section of Terrestrial Ecology, Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

^b Section for Genetics, Ecology & Evolution, Department of Biology, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Behaviour
Collembola
Copper contamination
Ecotoxicology
Temperature preference

ABSTRACT

Behavioural thermoregulation (thermotaxis) is essential for soil invertebrates to evade thermal extremes in terrestrial environments. Extensive and continuous use of copper (Cu) based products has led to elevated Cu concentration in soils across the globe and in some areas reaching concentrations that are hazardous to soil invertebrates. We hypothesised that environmental stressors, for example, exposure to heavy metals may compromise the adaptive behavioural thermoregulation of organisms, but very little is known of such interactions. In this study, we chose Cu as a model toxicant and investigated the potential effect of Cu-contaminated soils on the behavioural thermoregulation of springtails (*Folsomia candida*). We measured the distribution of springtails when placed on a temperature gradient ranging from 6 to 46 °C and estimated their thermal preference as an indicator of behavioural thermoregulation. Results showed that within 60 min of being introduced to the thermal gradient, the distribution of springtails was unimodal with slight skewness towards high temperature. Springtails exhibited a consistent preferred temperature range of approximately 21–23 °C across all Cu exposure levels and time points. However, Cu contamination increased the frequency of springtails recorded along the gradient where temperature was above 30 °C. We interpreted this observation as Cu-exposed animals having an elevated risk of entering heat coma and not being able to evade noxious temperatures. We conclude that Cu contamination does not alter the thermal preference of *F. candida* but compromises their ability to tolerate extreme high temperature. Incorporating behavioural responses into ecotoxicological assessments provides ecologically relevant insights into the impacts of chemical pollution on soil ecosystems.

1. Introduction

Copper (Cu) is an essential industrial element widely emitted by smelting works, industrial processes and agricultural practices such as use of fungicides, fertilisers, and growth enhancers (Lamichhane et al., 2018). In addition, recent studies have raised concerns about Cu-containing pig slurry (since Cu is used as a food additive for piglets) that has been applied to agricultural soil for decades (Formentini et al., 2015; Jensen et al., 2016). Extensive use of these Cu-based products has led to elevated Cu concentrations in soils across the globe (Chen et al., 2022; Durães et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019). Uptake and accumulation of Cu in the bodies of soil invertebrates can lead to adverse effects on the abundance, diversity and distribution of soil organisms and negatively influence soil fertility (Menezes-Oliveira et al., 2013; Mirmonsef et al., 2017; Naveed et al., 2014).

Springtails (Collembola) are abundant in soils from tropical to polar

areas (Potapov et al., 2023), and they are widely recommended as indicators and model species for ecological and ecotoxicological studies (Fountain and Hopkin, 2005; Hopkin, 1997; Lukić, 2019; OECD, 2016). The species *Folsomia candida* Willem is an ideal organism for laboratory experiments because it is easy to culture and has short generation times (Fountain and Hopkin, 2005). In recent years, several attempts have been made to explore the potential of *F. candida* in ethological studies regarding locomotion, movement pattern, avoidance and jumping behaviour (Auclerc et al., 2010; Boiteau et al., 2011; Brackenbury and Hunt, 1993; Kim and An, 2020; Sørensen et al., 1995). These findings revealed that behaviour was a much more sensitive endpoint for the effects of contaminants than conventional physiological endpoints (Boiteau et al., 2011; Kim and An, 2019; Kwak and An, 2016; Sørensen et al., 1995).

Behavioural avoidance is a crucial strategy for animals to avoid or escape from external stressors before involving costly physiological or

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: jian.ge@ecos.au.dk, wyyzge@gmail.com (J. Ge).

molecular responses protecting against the stressor (Dillon et al., 2012; Huey et al., 2012). Phototaxis, chemotaxis and thermotaxis are examples of organisms relocating to a potentially more secure habitat when exposed to a stressor (Boiteau and Mackinley, 2012, 2014; Fox et al., 2007; Gainer et al., 2022). Living in an environment with highly variable thermal conditions, soil arthropods are often subjected to temperature fluctuations not only from diurnal or seasonal variations of air temperatures but also from extreme weather events like heat waves (Evelt et al., 2012; Stéfanon et al., 2014). Behaviourally navigating toward benign temperatures could then serve as a method of optimising performance, for instance, moving away from the soil surface heated by direct sunlight into the deeper soil layers to mitigate the risks of exposure. However, the number of studies on thermal preference or thermotaxis of springtails is limited (Babenko, 1993; Boiteau and Mackinley, 2012; Hayward et al., 2003). Babenko (1993) was the first to investigate the temperature preference in 22 springtail species from the Arctic, showing a preferred temperature ranging from 9 to 18 °C. Hayward et al. (2003) studied the effects of temperature acclimation on the thermal preferences of an Antarctic springtail, *Cryptopygus antarcticus*, and found a positive correlation between acclimation temperature and temperature preference. Similar setups with cold and warm acclimation but shorter exposure periods were examined for *F. candida*, a temperate springtail species common in Europe and North America (Boiteau and Mackinley, 2012). These authors found that the preferred temperature of *F. candida* acclimated at 20 °C was ca. 9–12 °C, whereas the preference shifted to 6–9 °C when they were cold acclimated at 10 °C (Boiteau and Mackinley, 2012).

Effects of toxicants on the temperature preference of invertebrates have rarely been investigated. The paucity of research is possibly related to the complexity and variation of the behaviour of invertebrates, making it challenging to define behavioural norms and identify chemical effects. To our knowledge, only two studies have assessed thermotaxis behaviour of ectotherms in an ecotoxicological context. One showed that exposing zebrafish larvae to ibuprofen significantly prolonged the time they spent at suboptimal temperatures in a temperature gradient (Henry et al., 2022). The other study by Zhang et al. (2019) identified that diazepam, hexachlorophene and tetraethylthiuram disulfide disrupted the thermotaxis behaviour of regenerating tails of planarians. This finding suggested that psychopharmaceuticals may impact the function of transient receptor potential (TRP) channels, which were found to be the molecular pathway of temperature sensation (Dhaka et al., 2006; Hamada et al., 2008). However, thermotaxis depends not only on temperature sensation via TRP, which has previously been shown (Greppi et al., 2020; Takeshi et al., 2014; Zermoglio et al., 2015), but also on how the organism processes and responds to the received signals. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is recognised as one of the primary neurotransmitters in sensory and neuromuscular systems (Moser and Padilla, 2011; Soreq and Seidman, 2001). The inhibition of AChE by contaminants, including Cu (Howcroft et al., 2011), could therefore lead to behavioural abnormality (de Lima et al., 2013; Xuereb et al., 2009). From what has been reported, it appears that exposure to various toxicants can change the avoidance behaviour and locomotion of springtails (Kwak and An, 2016; Oliveira et al., 2015; Sørensen et al., 1995; Szabó et al., 2018), suggesting that chemicals might intervene in signal conduction and/or responsive performance. Therefore, it is possible that the thermal preference and thermotaxis behaviour of springtails will be altered by chemical contamination through compromised sensory systems.

In the present study, we investigated the distribution of *F. candida* on a thermal gradient device adapted to springtails. To assess the effects of chemical pollution, *F. candida* was exposed to Cu-contaminated soils for three weeks prior to the behavioural trials. We predicted that *F. candida* actively sense and behaviourally react to temperature change, leading to a unimodal distribution along the temperature gradient, with the preferred temperature at a benign range. Further, we hypothesised that exposure to Cu-contaminated soils compromise their sensory and/or

neuromuscular system, resulting in altered thermal preference and thermotaxis behaviour.

2. Materials & method

2.1. Animals

The test species *Folsomia candida* (Willem) was cultured in Petri dishes floored with plaster of Paris (moist gypsum/charcoal, 8:1, w/w), kept at 20 ± 0.2 °C with a photoperiod of 12 L:12D and fed dried baker's yeast. Adults of similar sizes were transferred to Petri dishes and left for 48 h to obtain age-synchronized eggs. Upon hatching, the juveniles were fed dry baker's yeast for 12 days prior to the Cu exposure.

2.2. Cu exposure

Agricultural soils contaminated by Cu were collected from a former timber preservation factory at Hygum (Jutland, Denmark), where the soil Cu concentrations have been well-characterised (Scott-Fordsmand et al., 2000). This field site had not been treated with pesticides for at least 20 years, and no other contaminants than Cu were found at the site (Nielsen et al., 2015; Pedersen et al., 1999). Soil from the upper 20 cm layer was dug out from three areas representing 'low', 'medium', and 'high' levels of Cu contamination. These three soil samples contained 17.3 ± 0.5 , 435.7 ± 6.9 and 1628.9 ± 15.6 mg Cu/kg dry weight (mean \pm SE; $n = 3$), respectively (Ge et al., 2023). The soil was dried at 80 °C for 48 h and sifted through a 2 mm mesh before use. Approximately 70 juvenile springtails (with an age of 12 d) were transferred to a conical plastic beaker (7.8 cm depth, 4.6 cm bottom diameter, 6.1 cm upper diameter) filled with 60 g Cu-contaminated soil moistened with tap water to 21% of soil dry weight. The number of replicates for each Cu level was 8. The springtails were then kept at 20 °C for three weeks. A previous study showed that the internal Cu concentration of springtails exposed for 3 weeks at 20 °C in these soils were 42.3 ± 1.5 , 47.1 ± 1.5 , and 81.6 ± 1.9 mg/kg dry weight (mean \pm SE; $n = 3$) at 'low', 'medium', and 'high' Cu contamination levels, respectively (Ge et al., 2023). During the experiment, animals were fed with dried baker's yeast, and the beakers were aerated every second day by briefly releasing the lids. At the end of exposure, soils in the beakers were poured into a plastic tray to collect the adult springtails by use of an aspirator. The remaining soil was then compressed to floor a new Petri dish for the extracted animals. Subsequently, the petri dishes with compressed soil and animals were placed in a temperature incubator at 20 °C until the following trials.

2.3. Thermal gradient apparatus

The thermal gradient device was designed and described in detail by Ritchie et al. (2021). In brief, the device was composed of a solid aluminium plate mounted with inserted copper pipes at both ends. The thermal gradient was created by heating at one end and cooling at the other end of the aluminium block, using circulating water baths pumping cold/hot water through the copper tubes at the ends of the aluminium block. To adapt the device for research on springtails, 9 aluminium U-Profiles (length 77 cm \times width 2 cm \times depth 2 cm) floored with a 2 mm layer of moistened Plaster of Paris were adhered to the aluminium heating block using heat-conducting silicone grease (Fig. 1A). Transparent rulers with scale were used as lids for the U-Profile-made arenas always keeping the plaster moist (Fig. 1B). In this experiment, the temperatures of water bath machines on the cold and hot ends were set at -0.5 and 50 °C, respectively. Upon thermal equilibrium, the temperature on top of the plaster of Paris of each arena was measured at every 5 cm using a fine copper-constantan thermo-couple connected to a Grant Squirrel 1250 datalogger (Grant 160 Instruments, Cambridge, UK). Thermal linearity along the gradient was then tested and confirmed (Supplementary Table S1). The actual temperature

Fig. 1. A diagram (A) and photo (B) of thermal gradient device refined specifically for thermotaxis test on Collembola based on the original design by Ritchie et al. (2021). The thermal device is composed of a solid aluminium plate as the base of arena and copper pipes at both ends. The thermal gradient was created by heating and cooling using circulating water baths pumping cold/hot water through copper tubes at both ends of the heating block. To better adjust the device for Collembola, 9 aluminium U-Profiles floored with plaster of Paris were adhered to the aluminium heating block using heat-conducting silicone grease.

gradient on the arena ranged from ca. 6.4–45.9 °C (± 0.1 °C) with a slope of 0.5 °C/cm (Supplementary Table S1).

2.4. Thermotaxis tests

About 70 springtails from each Cu exposure level were placed in the centre of the arena (at ca. 26.1 °C), and the position on the arena of each individual was recorded after 5, 15, 30 and 60 min, respectively, using a DJI pocket 2 camera (DJI, Shenzhen, China). Firstly, this protocol was conducted without any thermal gradient to test whether springtails would have a random distribution along the arena. We used three replicates for the test without a temperature gradient and confirmed that, at all Cu levels, the distribution of springtails was not significantly different from random with multiple peaks on individual frequency plots (Supplementary Fig. S1 and Table S2). Thus, distribution of the springtails in the test arenas with a thermal gradient was not confounded by other factors such as light.

Next, for the thermal preference test with a temperature gradient, we used eight replicates of 70 animals for each Cu treatment. The assigned arenas for springtails were fully randomised among Cu treatments. The plaster of Paris on the arena was moistened using deionised water, and the stability of the thermal gradient was reconfirmed before the start of every trial.

2.5. Statistics

Simple linear regression was conducted to confirm the linearity of the thermal gradient on top of the plaster of Paris in the arena using

GraphPad Prism 10.2.1 (GraphPad, Boston, MA, United States). To test for deviation from a random distribution when springtails were placed in the arenas without a temperature gradient, we employed chi-square tests using the ‘chisq.test’ function in the ‘stat’ package in R (ver. 4.2.2) (R Core Team, 2021). The position of each springtail in arenas with a temperature gradient was used to calculate the corresponding temperature using the coefficient and intercept reported in Supplementary Table S1. The cumulative frequency of springtails against temperature was calculated and used to fit a five-parameter log-logistic model (Equation (1)) using the ‘drc’ package (Ritz et al., 2016) in R.

$$\text{Freq}(\text{temp}) = c + \frac{d - c}{\left(1 + \exp(b(\log(\text{temp}) - \log(e)))\right)^f} \quad (1)$$

where $\text{Freq}(\text{temperature})$ describes the cumulative frequency of springtails as temperature increases along the gradient, c and d are the values of horizontal asymptotes, b describes how rapidly the curve makes its transition between two asymptotes (slope parameter), e is a location parameter of the highest slope and f describes the asymmetry of the curve.

Temperatures at which 20% and 80% of cumulative frequency was reached were defined as P_{20} and P_{80} , respectively. The temperature range between P_{20} and P_{80} was defined as thermal breadth (T_{bre}) (Fig. 2). The cumulative frequency curves were transformed into probability distribution curves to estimate the preferred temperature (T_{pre}), which is the temperature of the highest probability. The springtails appearing at temperatures above 30 °C were observed to be immobile and were marked as ‘heat coma’; The fraction of springtails in heat coma was defined as F_{hot} . These parameters were calculated for each replicate ($n =$

Fig. 2. Example of frequency distribution for extracting parameters related to thermal preference. Points are the cumulative frequency of springtails along the temperature gradient. The black curve is the fitted five-parameter log-logistic model (Eq. (1)), and the red curve is the transformed frequency distribution originating from one test arena. The temperature where the highest transformed probability occurs, 20% and 80% of cumulative frequency, are the preferred temperature (T_{pre}), P_{20} and P_{80} , respectively. Temperature range bridging P_{20} and P_{80} is defined as thermal breadth (T_{bre}). The springtails found above 30 °C are counted as springtails in heat coma giving the fraction (F_{hot}).

8) and subjected to analysis of variance using linear mixed-effects models in R with pairwise t-tests adjusted by Bonferroni correction. Exposure time and Cu exposure levels were defined as fixed effects, and the numbers of replicates (i.e. test arenas) were defined as random effects in the models. The significance level was set as $P < 0.05$.

3. Results

When a temperature gradient was created on the arena, springtails placed at the centre quickly responded to temperature, and formed a distribution differing significantly from a uniform distribution (Fig. 3 and Supplementary Fig. S1). The cumulative frequency started at 10 °C and later increased steeply from ca. 0.1 to 0.9 at temperatures between 20 and 25 °C. Distribution at high temperature was detached by a gap at ca. 30 °C. The cumulative frequency above 30 °C quickly increased until ca. 38 °C (Fig. 3). Springtails at different time points distributed themselves in a similar pattern regardless of levels of Cu exposure.

From the extracted parameters, the T_{pre} of springtails was found to be ca. 21–23 °C independent of time and Cu exposure levels (Tables 1 and 2). The T_{bre} was significantly reduced with time from ca. 5 °C (after 5 min) to 3 °C after 60 min, whereas no effect of Cu exposure was observed (Tables 1 and 2). The temperature of the lower 20% fractile (P_{20}) was ca. 20 °C, and was not influenced by either time or Cu exposure. However, P_{80} significantly decreased with time (Table 2) and slightly increased for springtails in the medium Cu exposure group ($P = 0.058$). The fraction of springtails being trapped in a hot area was significantly increased by Cu exposure (doubled at “High Cu” after 60 min; Table 1) but was not affected by time (Table 2). No interaction of time and Cu exposure was found in any of the selected parameters.

4. Discussion

Thermotaxis is a behavioural strategy to regulate body temperature for Collembola to expand their habitat in thermally heterogeneous environments but this behaviour could be compromised by toxicants in the environment via altered energetic allocation (Jager et al., 2004), damaged sensory cells (Wang and Wang, 2023) or restrained neuromuscular function (Gauthier et al., 2016). In this study, we aimed to investigate if thermotaxis of springtails would be influenced by Cu in a concentration known to cause adverse effects on growth, reproduction and membrane lipid composition of *F. candida* (Ge et al., 2023). Despite exposure to such stressful levels of Cu, our findings suggest that Cu contamination does not change the preferred temperature or thermal scope of the test species, but we did observe a reduced ability to escape from high temperature exposure, when the animals inadvertently moved into these areas of the arenas. This suggests that Cu pollution could exacerbate the increased risk of heat failure predicted for soil arthropods (and other ectotherms) in a warming climate (Jørgensen et al., 2022).

In accordance with our hypothesis, springtails quickly responded to the thermal gradient and distributed unimodally, which greatly differed from the distribution without thermal gradient regardless of factors of time and Cu exposure. The preferred temperature was 22.7 °C, which is in line with the results from Fox et al. (2007)’s study showing that springtails avoid 30 °C and move into colder areas at 22 °C, even if there were only two temperatures included in their study. This estimate of preferred temperature falls within the optimal temperature range for survival and growth and is slightly lower than the optimal temperature for reproduction (Ge et al., 2023).

We observed a decreasing thermal breadth with time, which is a proof of behavioural thermoregulation in that more springtails displayed their preference. Specifically, the decrease of thermal breadth was asymmetric, with a slight increase in boundary towards low temperature and rapid reduction in boundary towards high temperature. It could be speculated that springtails avoided low temperature and had more plasticity towards high temperature. Ecologically speaking, entering a temperature lower than 20 °C will compromise mobility, growth, and reproduction, and the only probable benefit from choosing a colder environment may be longer life expectancy (Roeben et al., 2023). However, temperatures slightly higher than 22 °C could increase somatic growth and reproduction output (Ge et al., 2023; Roeben et al., 2023). Boiteau and Mackinley (2012) created a similar thermal gradient for thermal preference test on *F. candida*, but the results were substantially different from our study. Thus, these authors found that the highest occurrence of animals was at 6–9 °C for cold-acclimated *F. candida*, and 9–12 °C for control animals acclimated at 20 °C. These preferred temperatures are much lower than what we have found (22 °C), likely due to differences in methodology. Hence, Boiteau and Mackinley (2012) placed springtails evenly along the entire thermal gradient at the beginning of the trial. Low temperatures would instantly reduce the mobility of springtails (Ge et al., 2024), leading to high frequency of animals trapped at low temperatures, and not a result of active thermal preference. In the present study, we placed springtails in the centre of an arena where locomotion was not hampered by sub-optimal temperature and hence giving the animals better opportunity to explore and move to temperatures of preference. As for low temperature, springtails being placed in the area of high temperature would likely accumulate heat damages (Wehrli et al., 2024; Xie et al., 2022). It should be noted that springtails could benefit from rapid heat hardening, which has been found to increase heat tolerance in other species (Alemu et al., 2017; Sørensen et al., 2019) and may, therefore, influence the distribution of springtails on the thermal gradient.

Directional movements or navigating ability requires a sophisticated sensory and neuromuscular system, which is apparently missing in eyeless arthropod species (Hopkin, 1997). Collembola adopts a Brownian movement pattern to forage for resources, but this random movement pattern will transit to be more directional upon the occurrence of

Fig. 3. Frequency distribution of springtails *Folsomia candida* along a temperature gradient. Columns indicate frequency at different time points, whereas rows indicate the frequency under different Cu-exposure levels. Coloured points are the cumulative frequency of springtails on the thermal gradient, and the corresponding curves are the fits of five-parameter log-logistic models. Grey curves are individual probability models transformed from cumulative frequency curves. The Cu concentrations of 'low', 'medium', and 'high' Cu contaminated soils were 17.3 ± 0.5 , 435.7 ± 6.9 and 1628.9 ± 15.6 mg Cu/kg.

odour cues or other external stimuli (Auclerc et al., 2010; Chauvat et al., 2014). Supposedly, springtails exposed to a thermal gradient could avoid thermal extremes using similar strategy. However, nearly 5–10 % of springtails were trapped in an area with high temperatures up to 30–35 °C, with discontinuity between 27 °C and 30 °C. The springtails trapped in the hot area were observably immobile, likely in heat coma or dead. This previously unreported observation suggests that springtails in nature could inadvertently move into areas of high and damaging temperature causing mortality. Seemingly, this happened to 5–10 % of the springtails in the control soils. Combined with our previous findings that the mobility of springtails was the highest at 33 °C (Ge et al., 2024), we speculate that the strategy of the springtails was to keep walking fast to increase the chance of escaping zones of high temperature. Once springtails arrive in a cooler area, their stress level will reduce and they will tend to stay.

Many major chemical pollutants can cause neurotoxicity and for that reason ecotoxicologists are increasingly investigating behavioural responses or alterations of animals subjected to chemical exposure (Gainer et al., 2022; Hellou, 2011; Tooming et al., 2017). Compared to avoidance tests under constant environmental conditions, incorporating environmental factors into the assessment of behavioural toxicity is more ecologically relevant as free-ranging soil animals are living in highly variable environments. We found that Cu contamination had no

significant effect on the thermal preference nor on the breadth of the most preferred temperature range. However, we observed a significantly elevated risk of being trapped in a hot area with increasing levels of Cu contamination. Mechanistically speaking, the higher risk of heat coma and death may result from compromised sensory and neuromuscular systems after long-term exposure to Cu and, consequently, failure to detect and respond at an early stage before a fatal amount of heat damage has accumulated. Alternatively, springtails intoxicated by Cu might have accumulated more damage from high temperatures at a higher rate, resulting in faster deterioration in mobility.

Thermal performance, tolerance, and adaptation are inherently important for understanding how ectotherms interact with the most prominent environmental factor – temperature. We argue that incorporating thermal biology in ecotoxicology is a relevant new area of research which can help answer the inevitable question of how much impact animals receive from chemical pollution in a field situation, compared to the results from laboratory studies which mostly uses constant and optimal environmental conditions. Animals in suboptimal environments are usually more vulnerable to chemical exposure and vice versa (Holmstrup et al., 2014; Slotsbo et al., 2009). However, we should not neglect the thermoregulatory behaviour of organisms, which can help them avoid more costly responses at the physiological or genetic level (Huey et al., 2003). This being said, we may underestimate

Table 1

Extracted parameters related to the thermotaxis of springtails *Folsomia candida* exposed to low, medium and high Cu-contaminated soils for 3 weeks.

Time/ min	Cu	T_{pre}	T_{bre}	P_{20}	P_{80}	F_{hot}
5	Low	21.67 ± 1.03	5.53 ± 0.92	19.57 ± 0.98	25.10 ± 0.55	0.10 ± 0.02
	Medium	24.19 ± 0.67	5.54 ± 0.87	20.69 ± 0.72	26.24 ± 0.40	0.14 ± 0.03
	High	22.83 ± 0.88	5.85 ± 0.53	19.71 ± 0.72	25.56 ± 0.56	0.14 ± 0.03
15	Low	23.14 ± 0.89	3.78 ± 0.58	20.71 ± 0.62	24.49 ± 0.39	0.08 ± 0.02
	Medium	23.78 ± 0.64	3.98 ± 0.86	21.41 ± 0.59	25.39 ± 0.46	0.13 ± 0.03
	High	22.09 ± 0.76	4.63 ± 0.65	20.21 ± 0.81	24.85 ± 0.55	0.15 ± 0.03
30	Low	22.36 ± 0.99	3.66 ± 0.45	20.44 ± 0.69	24.10 ± 0.43	0.08 ± 0.02
	Medium	22.64 ± 0.44	3.86 ± 0.81	20.89 ± 0.81	24.75 ± 0.40	0.11 ± 0.03
	High	22.33 ± 0.69	2.87 ± 0.51	21.20 ± 0.71	24.07 ± 0.52	0.15 ± 0.03
60	Low	21.97 ± 0.61	3.29 ± 0.43	20.55 ± 0.50	23.84 ± 0.62	0.08 ± 0.02
	Medium	22.80 ± 0.45	3.27 ± 0.90	21.33 ± 0.47	24.60 ± 0.55	0.12 ± 0.03
	High	22.19 ± 0.65	2.42 ± 0.26	21.05 ± 0.66	23.46 ± 0.63	0.16 ± 0.03

Note: Data was presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). T_{pre} : preferred temperature; T_{bre} : thermal breadth between 20% and 80% cumulative frequency; P_{20} : temperature at 20% cumulative frequency; P_{80} : temperature at 80% cumulative frequency; F_{hot} : fraction of springtails being trapped by heat coma at temperature above 30 °C. The Cu concentrations of 'low', 'medium', and 'high' Cu contaminated soils were 17.3 ± 0.5, 435.7 ± 6.9 and 1628.9 ± 15.6 mg Cu/kg.

Table 2

Results of analysis of variance on the effects of time and Cu contamination on thermotaxis-related parameters of *Folsomia candida* using linear mixed-effects models.

Factor (DF)	T_{pre}	T_{bre}	P_{20}	P_{80}	F_{hot}
Cu (2, 87)	0.64 0.5288	0.32 0.7224	0.77 0.4657	2.94 0.0583	3.22 0.0474
Time (1, 76)	3.11 0.0820	27.68 <0.0001	5.32 0.0239	29.39 <0.0001	0.19 0.6656
Cu*Time (2, 76)	0.91 0.4085	1.30 0.2778	0.69 0.5038	0.80 0.4545	0.55 0.5812

Note: Data in the bracket shows the degrees of freedom. The upper value in the cell is F value, and lower value is P value, shown in bold italics if less than 0.05. T_{pre} : preferred temperature; T_{bre} : thermal breadth between 20% and 80% cumulative frequency; P_{20} : temperature at 20% cumulative frequency; P_{80} : temperature at 80% cumulative frequency; F_{hot} : fraction of springtails being trapped by heat coma at temperature above 30 °C. The Cu concentrations of 'low', 'medium', and 'high' Cu contaminated soils were 17.3 ± 0.5, 435.7 ± 6.9 and 1628.9 ± 15.6 mg Cu/kg.

the toxicity of contaminants but overestimate the negative consequences of global warming when confining our assessment to traditional endpoints under highly controlled and acute conditions not allowing behavioural avoidance. Thus, investigating behavioural responses to temperature and contaminants could fill the knowledge gap between impacts received from the external environment and the exact effects pressing on organisms. Integrating behavioural thermoregulation with thermal performance and tolerance in an ecotoxicological context could help us better interpret laboratory results, understand empirical data and make more ecologically relevant and accurate prediction.

Funding information

This study is funded by the CHRONIC project (No. 956009) 'Chronic exposure scenarios driving environmental risks of Chemicals', which is an Innovative Training Network (ITN) funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA). This publication reflects only the authors' view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jian Ge: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Stine Slotsbo:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Jesper Givskov Sørensen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Martin Holmstrup:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtherbio.2024.103950>.

References

- Alemu, T., Alemneh, T., Pertoldi, C., Ambelu, A., Bahrndorff, S., 2017. Costs and benefits of heat and cold hardening in a soil arthropod. *Biol. J. Linn. Soc.* 122, 765–773. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biolinnean/blx092>.
- Auclerc, A., Libourel, P.A., Salmon, S., Bels, V., Ponge, J.F., 2010. Assessment of movement patterns in *Folsomia candida* (Hexapoda: Collembola) in the presence of food. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 42, 657–659. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2009.12.012>.
- Babenko, A., 1993. Temperature preferendum of Collembola from the Arctic tundra of Taimyr. *Entomol. Rev.* 72, 89–101.
- Boiteau, G., Lynch, D.H., Mackinley, P., 2011. Avoidance tests with *Folsomia candida* for the assessment of copper contamination in agricultural soils. *Environ. Pollut.* 159, 903–906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2010.12.023>.
- Boiteau, G., Mackinley, P., 2012. Locomotor response of *Folsomia candida* (Collembola: Isotomidae) to cooling temperatures. *Environ. Entomol.* 41, 916–924. <https://doi.org/10.1603/en12008>.
- Boiteau, G., Mackinley, P., 2014. Geotaxis in the springtail *Folsomia candida*. *Entomol. Exp. Appl.* 152, 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eea.12195>.
- Brackenbury, J., Hunt, H., 1993. Jumping in springtails: mechanism and dynamics. *J. Zool.* 229, 217–236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.1993.tb02632.x>.
- Chauvat, M., Perez, G., Ponge, J.-F., 2014. Foraging patterns of soil springtails are impacted by food resources. *Appl. Soil Ecology* 82, 72–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2014.05.012>.
- Chen, L., Zhou, M., Wang, J., Zhang, Z., Duan, C., Wang, X., Zhao, S., Bai, X., Li, Z., Li, Z., Fang, L., 2022. A global meta-analysis of heavy metal(loid)s pollution in soils near copper mines: evaluation of pollution level and probabilistic health risks. *Sci. Total Environ.* 835, 155441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155441>.
- de Lima, D., Roque, G.M., de Almeida, E.A., 2013. In vitro and in vivo inhibition of acetylcholinesterase and carboxylesterase by metals in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). *Mar. Environ. Res.* 91, 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2012.11.005>.
- Dhaka, A., Viswanath, V., Patapoutian, A., 2006. Trp ION channels and temperature sensatION. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.* 29, 135–161. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.neuro.29.051605.112958>.
- Dillon, M.E., Liu, R., Wang, G., Huey, R.B., 2012. Disentangling thermal preference and the thermal dependence of movement in ectotherms. *J. Therm. Biol.* 37, 631–639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtherbio.2012.07.004>.
- Durães, N., Novo, L.A.B., Candeias, C., Da Silva, E.F., 2018. Distribution, Transport and Fate of Pollutants, Soil Pollution. Elsevier, pp. 29–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-849873-6.00002-9>.
- Evelt, S.R., Agam, N., Kustas, W.P., Colaizzi, P.D., Schwartz, R.C., 2012. Soil profile method for soil thermal diffusivity, conductivity and heat flux: comparison to soil heat flux plates. *Adv. Water Resour.* 50, 41–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2012.04.012>.
- Formentini, T.A., Mallmann, F.J.K., Pinheiro, A., Fernandes, C.V.S., Bender, M.A., da Veiga, M., dos Santos, D.R., Doelsch, E., 2015. Copper and zinc accumulation and

- fractionation in a clayey Hapludox soil subject to long-term pig slurry application. *Sci. Total Environ.* 536, 831–839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.07.110>.
- Fountain, M.T., Hopkin, S.P., 2005. *Folsomia CANDIDA* (collembola): a “standard” soil arthropod. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.* 50, 201–222. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.50.071803.130331>.
- Fox, G.L., Coyle-Thompson, C.A., Bellinger, P.F., Cohen, R.W., 2007. Phototactic responses to ultraviolet and white light in various species of Collembola, including the eyeless species, *Folsomia candida*. *J. Insect Sci.* 7, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1673/031.007.2201>.
- Gainer, A., Owojori, O.J., Maboeta, M., 2022. Use of soil invertebrate avoidance tests as an emerging tool in soil ecotoxicology. *Rev. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 260 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44169-021-00004-4>.
- Gauthier, P.T., Norwood, W.P., Prepas, E.E., Pyle, G.G., 2016. Behavioural alterations from exposure to Cu, phenanthrene, and Cu-phenanthrene mixtures: linking behaviour to acute toxic mechanisms in the aquatic amphipod, *Hyalella azteca*. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 170, 377–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2015.10.019>.
- Ge, J., Slotsbo, S., Sørensen, J.G., Holmstrup, M., 2023. Copper-contaminated soil compromises thermal performance in the springtail *Folsomia candida* (Collembola). *Sci. Total Environ.* 165334 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165334>.
- Ge, J., Sørensen, J.G., Slotsbo, S., Holmstrup, M., 2024. A method for assessing thermal preference and locomotion of a soil arthropod, *Folsomia candida* and its application in ecotoxicology. In: SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting. SETAC, Seville, Spain, pp. 41–42. <https://www.setac.org/asset/F43E9BD5-D572-44D2-908AA4BCFBD62871/>.
- Greppi, C., Laursen, W.J., Budelli, G., Chang, E.C., Daniels, A.M., Giesen, L.v., Smidler, A.L., Catteruccia, F., Garrity, P.A., 2020. Mosquito heat seeking is driven by an ancestral cooling receptor. *Science* 367, 681–684. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aay9847>.
- Hamada, F.N., Rosenzweig, M., Kang, K., Pulver, S.R., Ghezzi, A., Jegla, T.J., Garrity, P.A., 2008. An internal thermal sensor controlling temperature preference in *Drosophila*. *Nature* 454, 217–220. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature07001>.
- Hayward, S.A.L., Worland, M.R., Convey, P., Bale, J.S., 2003. Temperature preferences of the mite, *Alaskozetes antarcticus*, and the collembolan, *Cryptopygus antarcticus* from the maritime Antarctic. *Physiol. Entomol.* 28, 114–121. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3032.2003.00327.x>.
- Hellou, J., 2011. Behavioural ecotoxicology, an “early warning” signal to assess environmental quality. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 18, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-010-0367-2>.
- Henry, J., Bai, Y., Kreuder, F., Saaristo, M., Kaslin, J., Wlodkovic, D., 2022. A miniaturized electrothermal array for rapid analysis of temperature preference behaviors in ecology and ecotoxicology. *Environ. Pollut.* 314, 120202 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.120202>.
- Holmstrup, M., Bouvrais, H., Westh, P., Wang, C.H., Slotsbo, S., Waagner, D., Engbrok, K., Ipsen, J.H., 2014. Lipophilic contaminants influence cold tolerance of invertebrates through changes in cell membrane fluidity. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48, 9797–9803. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es502221g>.
- Hopkin, S.P., 1997. *Biology of the Springtails: (Insecta: Collembola)*. OUP, Oxford.
- Howcroft, C.F., Gravato, C., Amorim, M.J.B., Novais, S.C., Soares, A.M.V.M., Guilhermino, L., 2011. Biochemical characterization of cholinesterases in *Enchytraeus albidus* and assessment of in vivo and in vitro effects of different soil properties, copper and phenmedipham. *Ecotoxicology* 20, 119–130. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10646-010-0562-4>.
- Huey, Raymond B., Hertz, Paul E., Sinervo, B., 2003. Behavioral drive versus behavioral inertia in evolution: a null model approach. *Am. Nat.* 161, 357–366. <https://doi.org/10.1086/346135>.
- Huey, R.B., Kearney, M.R., Krockenberger, A., Holtum, J.A.M., Jess, M., Williams, S.E., 2012. Predicting organismal vulnerability to climate warming: roles of behaviour, physiology and adaptation. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B: Biol. Sci.* 367, 1665–1679. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2012.0005>.
- Jager, T., Crommentuijn, T., van Gestel, C.A.M., Kooijman, S.A.L.M., 2004. Simultaneous modeling of multiple end points in life-cycle toxicity tests. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 38, 2894–2900. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0352348>.
- Jensen, J., Larsen, M.M., Bak, J., 2016. National monitoring study in Denmark finds increased and critical levels of copper and zinc in arable soils fertilized with pig slurry. *Environ. Pollut.* 214, 334–340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.03.034>.
- Jørgensen, L.B., Ørsted, M., Malte, H., Wang, T., Overgaard, J., 2022. Extreme escalation of heat failure rates in ectotherms with global warming. *Nature* 611, 93–98. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05334-4>.
- Kim, S.W., An, Y.-J., 2019. Soil microplastics inhibit the movement of springtail species. *Environ. Int.* 126, 699–706. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.02.067>.
- Kim, S.W., An, Y.-J., 2020. Edible size of polyethylene microplastics and their effects on springtail behavior. *Environ. Pollut.* 266, 115255 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115255>.
- Kwak, J.I., An, Y.-J., 2016. Trophic transfer of silver nanoparticles from earthworms disrupts the locomotion of springtails (Collembola). *J. Hazard. Mater.* 315, 110–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2016.05.005>.
- Lamichhane, J.R., Osdaghi, E., Behlau, F., Köhl, J., Jones, J.B., Aubertot, J.-N., 2018. Thirteen decades of antimicrobial copper compounds applied in agriculture. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 38 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-018-0503-9>.
- Li, C., Zhou, K., Qin, W., Tian, C., Qi, M., Yan, X., Han, W., 2019. A review on heavy metals contamination in soil: effects, sources, and remediation techniques. *Soil sediment contam. Int. J.* 28, 380–394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15320383.2019.1592108>.
- Lukić, M., 2019. Chapter 35 - Collembola. In: White, W.B., Culver, D.C., Pipan, T. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Caves*, third ed. Academic Press, pp. 308–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814124-3.00034-0>.
- Menezes-Oliveira, V.B., Scott-Fordsmand, J.J., Soares, A.M.V.M., Amorim, M.J.B., 2013. Effects of temperature and copper pollution on soil community - extreme temperature events can lead to community extinction. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 32, 2678–2685. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.2345>.
- Mirmonsef, H., Hornum, H.D., Jensen, J., Holmstrup, M., 2017. Effects of an aged copper contamination on distribution of earthworms, reproduction and cocoon hatchability. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 135, 267–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2016.10.012>.
- Moser, V.C., Padilla, S., 2011. Esterase metabolism of cholinesterase inhibitors using rat liver in vitro. *Toxicology* 281, 56–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tox.2011.01.002>.
- Naveed, M., Moldrup, P., Arthur, E., Holmstrup, M., Nicolaisen, M., Tuller, M., Herath, L., Hamamoto, S., Kawamoto, K., Komatsu, T., Vogel, H.-J., Wollesen De Jonge, L., 2014. Simultaneous loss of soil biodiversity and functions along a copper contamination gradient: when soil goes to sleep. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 78, 1239–1250. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2014.02.0052>.
- Nielsen, M.T., Scott-Fordsmand, J.J., Murphy, M.W., Kristiansen, S.M., 2015. Speciation and solubility of copper along a soil contamination gradient. *J. Soils Sediments* 15, 1558–1570. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-015-1109-3>.
- OECD, 2016. Test No. 232: collembolan reproduction test in soil. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264264601-en>.
- Oliveira, M., Cardoso, D.N., Soares, A.M.V.M., Loureiro, S., 2015. Effects of short-term exposure to fluoxetine and carbamazepine to the collembolan *Folsomia candida*. *Chemosphere* 120, 86–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.06.038>.
- Pedersen, M.B., Axelsen, J.r.A., Strandberg, B., Jensen, J., Attrill, M.J., 1999. The impact of a copper gradient on a microarthropod field community. *Ecotoxicology* 8, 467–483. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008964021344>.
- Potapov, A.M., Guerra, C.A., van den Hoogen, J., Babenko, A., Bellini, B.C., Berg, M.P., Chown, S.L., Deharveng, L., Kováč, L., Kuznetsova, N.A., Ponge, J.-F., Potapov, M.B., Russell, D.J., Alexandre, D., Alatalo, J.M., Arbea, J.I., Bandyopadhyaya, I., Bernava, V., Bokhorst, S., Bolger, T., Castaño-Meneses, G., Chauvat, M., Chen, T.-W., Chomel, M., Classen, A.T., Cortet, J., Cúchta, P., Manuela de la Pedrosa, A., Ferreira, S.S.D., Fiera, C., Filser, J., Franken, O., Fujii, S., Koudjij, E.G., Gao, M., Gendreau-Berthiaume, B., Gomez-Pamies, D.F., Greve, M., Tanya Handa, I., Heiniger, C., Holmstrup, M., Homet, P., Ivask, M., Janion-Scheepers, C., Jochum, M., Joimel, S., Claudia, S., Jorge, B., Jucevica, E., Ferlian, O., Iuñes de Oliveira Filho, L. C., Klauberg-Filho, O., Baretta, D., Krab, E.J., Kuu, A., de Lima, E.C.A., Lin, D., Lindo, Z., Liu, A., Lu, J.-Z., Lucíañez, M.J., Marx, M.T., McCarty, M.A., Minor, M.A., Nakamori, T., Negri, L., Ochoa-Hueso, R., Palacios-Vargas, J.G., Pollierer, M.M., Querner, P., Raschmanová, N., Rashid, M.I., Raymond-Léonard, L.J., Rousseau, L., Saifutdinov, R.A., Salmon, S., Sayer, E.J., Scheunemann, N., Scholz, C., Seeber, J., Shveenkov, Y.B., Stebaeva, S.K., Sterzynska, M., Sun, X., Susanti, W.I., Tskaveka, A. A., Thakur, M.P., Tsiafouli, M.A., Turnbull, M.S., Twala, M.N., Uvarov, A.V., Venier, L.A., Widenfalk, L.A., Winck, B.R., Winkler, D., Wu, D., Xie, Z., Yin, R., Zeppelini, D., Crowther, T.W., Eisenhauer, N., Scheu, S., 2023. Globally invariant metabolism but density-diversity mismatch in springtails. *Nat. Commun.* 14, 674. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36216-6>.
- R Core Team, 2021. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- Ritchie, M.W., Dawson, J.W., MacMillan, H.A., 2021. A simple and dynamic thermal gradient device for measuring thermal performance in small ectotherms. *Curr. Res. Insect Sci.* 1, 100005 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cris.2020.100005>.
- Ritz, C., Baty, F., Streibig, J.C., Gerhard, D., 2016. Dose-Response analysis using R. *PLoS One* 10, e0146021. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0146021>.
- Roeben, V., Montoya-Tzschoppe, L., Roß-Nickoll, M., 2023. Long life at low temperatures – the life-history of *Folsomia candida* at ecological relevant temperatures. *Pedobiologia* 96, 150847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedobi.2022.150847>.
- Scott-Fordsmand, J.J., Krogh, P.H., Weeks, J.M., 2000. Responses of *Folsomia fimetaria* (Collembola: isotomidae) to copper under different soil copper contamination histories in relation to risk assessment. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 19, 1297–1303. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5620190511>.
- Slotsbo, S., Heckmann, L.H., Damgaard, C., Roelofs, D., de Boer, T., Holmstrup, M., 2009. Exposure to mercury reduces heat tolerance and heat hardening ability of the springtail *Folsomia candida*. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. Chimia: Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 150, 118–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpc.2009.04.001>.
- Sørensen, F.F., Bayley, M., Baatrup, E., 1995. The effects of sublethal dimethoate exposure on the locomotor behavior of the collembolan *Folsomia candida* (Isotomidae). *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 14, 1587–1590. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5620190511>.
- Sørensen, M.H., Kristensen, T.N., Lauritzen, J.M.S., Noer, N.K., Høye, T.T., Bahrndorff, S., 2019. Rapid induction of the heat hardening response in an Arctic insect. *Biol. Lett.* 15, 20190613 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2019.0613>.
- Soreq, H., Seidman, S., 2001. Acetylcholinesterase - new roles for an old actor. *Rev. Neurosci.* 2, 294–302. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35067589>.
- Stéfanon, M., Drobinski, P., D’Andrea, F., Lebeaupin-Brossier, C., Bastin, S., 2014. Soil moisture-temperature feedbacks at meso-scale during summer heat waves over Western Europe. *Clim. Dynam.* 42, 1309–1324. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-013-1794-9>.
- Szabó, B., Seres, A., Bakonyi, G., 2018. *Folsomia candida* (Collembola) locomotor activity pattern is changed by a neurotoxicant pesticide. *Acta Zool. Acad. Sci. Hungar.* 64, 355–368. <https://doi.org/10.17109/AZH.64.4.355.2018>.
- Takeshi, I., Taiga, Y., Kiyokazu, A., 2014. Thermosensory signaling by TRPM is processed by brain serotonergic neurons to produce planarian thermotaxis. *J. Neurosci.* 34, 15701 <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.5379-13.2014>.

- Tooming, E., Merivee, E., Must, A., Merivee, M.-I., Sibul, I., Nurme, K., Williams, I.H., 2017. Behavioural effects of the neonicotinoid insecticide thiamethoxam on the predatory insect *Platynus assimilis*. *Ecotoxicology* 26, 902–913. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10646-017-1820-5>.
- Wang, X., Wang, W.-X., 2023. Cu(I)/Cu(II) released by Cu nanoparticles revealed differential cellular toxicity related to mitochondrial dysfunction. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 57, 9548–9558. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.3c00864>.
- Wehrli, M., Slotsbo, S., Ge, J., Holmstrup, M., 2024. Acclimation temperature influences the thermal sensitivity of injury accumulation in *Folsomia candida* at extreme low and high temperatures. *Curr. Res. Insect Sci.* 6, 100089 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cris.2024.100089>.
- Xie, L., Slotsbo, S., Holmstrup, M., 2022. Tolerance of high temperature and associated effects on reproduction in euedaphic Collembola. *J. Therm. Biol.* 103439 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtherbio.2022.103439>.
- Xuereb, B., Lefevre, E., Garric, J., Geffard, O., 2009. Acetylcholinesterase activity in *Gammarus fossarum* (Crustacea Amphipoda): linking AChE inhibition and behavioural alteration. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 94, 114–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2009.06.010>.
- Zermoglio, P.F., Latorre-Estivalis, J.M., Crespo, J.E., Lorenzo, M.G., Lazzari, C.R., 2015. Thermosensation and the TRPV channel in *Rhodnius prolixus*. *J. Insect Physiol.* 81, 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2015.07.014>.
- Zhang, S., Hagstrom, D., Hayes, P., Graham, A., Collins, E.-M.S., 2019. Multi-behavioral endpoint testing of an 87-chemical compound library in freshwater planarians. *Toxicol. Sci.* 167, 26–44. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfy145>.